

THE NEW APPROACHES TO THE CONCEPT OF TRANSLATION THEORY AND PRACTICE.

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Abstract. This abstract is designed for university students as well as intelligent explorers. This article about the educational value of translational theory. In this abstract is expressed about approaches to the translation theory in our modern society, the role of the internship during the our lifestyle and for our career. In addition about the formation of the skills the processing practice. Most importantly it discusses the concept of translational theory and theoretical basis of the article evaluation and methodology.

Key words: Theory, translation, modern, practice, skills, explorers, automatically.

INTRODUCTION

First of all before explaining we have to pay attention to the meaning of the word translation it does not mean simply, means transferring the meaning of words from one language to another, but rather it is a complex process that includes a series of phases. These include first reading a segment of the original text. The next step is understanding as a whole, which does not stop at that of individual words. The translation can be done manually by human translators or automatically by computer programs, also human translation is more accurately for complex and culturally specific content. As well as secondly about theory. It is a supposition or a system of ideas intended to explain something, especially one based on general principles of the thing to be explained. It considers translations as a process of interpreting texts, in addition involves converting written or spoken content from the source language, taking into account linguistic, cultural and idiomatic differences between the two languages. The translation requires a deep understanding of both the source and target, as well as cultural nuances and context. Next one is about practice. The full meaning of the practice is to perform or work at repeatedly so as to become proficient. If we practice more and more, consequently it will benefit to our whole life. Without practice no people achieve nothing, no scientist achieved without it. As mentioned Lao

Tzu <Practice silence. It is a source of great strength>. Exactly it is a great specimen about this topic, uzbek ancient scientists also emphase to learning more and practicing and of course after striving the people can be achieve all of them. The challenges require many things. In fact for gaining something, humans have to sacrifice from something.

Methods

Merits and Demerits of translation.

Merits of translation:

Facilities communication: Translation enables people to communicate effectively, fostering understanding and collaboration across culture and culture.

Preserves knowledge and culture: It helps literature, historical documents, scientific research and cultural heritage.

Enhancing learning: Translation aids language learning, helping them improve vocabulary, grammar and comprehension skills.

Loss of nuance and context: Translating complex or culturally-specific concepts may results in the loss of nuances, idiomatic expressions and contextual meanings.

Difficulty in Translating Untranslatable Elements: may be challenging to translate accurately.

Actually the role of translation plays an essential part in our modern assembly. It is crucial, because not everyone speaks English. The translation connects to Global Economy. Translation speech ideas and information. Translation is independent and radically different. In order to translate need four skills, four language competences; reading, writing, speaking and also listening. During the learning this profession firstly will have to analyze about this job. Like, everything else, there are different methods of translation and they vary in form and function. There are quite viable translations. For example translating novels, poems, original text or translating theatre, opera, dialogue, lyrics and etc. The basic analyses on translation divide into several stages.

- *Analysis number one- to enhance the more vocabulary.*
- *Speak accurately, fluently and culturally.*
- *Learning to listen the another speakers.*
- *Communicate politely the process of translation.*

The translation has the formal types. There are *general translation, legal translation, literary translation.*

The general translation it is a source materials mostly uses terms and ordinary, everyday speech. It commonly uses with general type, utilizes in social society. Legal translation one of the more complex and complicated professional translation types out there. Legal translation is best described as the translation of many other legal documents. Literary translation-literary refers to as the name of translation, it will be done for literature, such as poems, novels and short stories.

In grammatical translation divide into several stages. There are quite specimens.

1. Word for word translation. Nowadays many younges utilize from social media form for translating their work automatically,ultimately this kind of translation type can render them from word to word and it considers the common mistake.Basically some words can not be translated from word to word. The first one is the idioma.
2. Paraphrasing: typically explains or clarifies the text that is being paraphrased.

Results and Dicussion

As a matter of fact there are many benefit sides of translation. The ability to render the sentences to another language is most important human quality. Whener the young generation explore the translation,consequently they lay the foundation to their prospect. Nowadays they have the best opportunities. For instance after learning they have to study. In addition they have to work as a computer programmer if they know the languages. Most importantly they can contribute to the prosperity of the country. If in the world increase the many translators the our country can work with other foreign countries collaboratively and essentively part is it will enhance to our county's level. In this reason in present days are paying attention to the translation. Whenever the tourists visit to our country, they need the translators. After that they have to earn a lot of money as well as it will benefit to their financial side. Translation includes the development of a number of practical aspects related to the method of teaching translation as well as various practical issues the solution of which contributes to the successful implementation of its functions as a translator. The theory of translation enable to people to view results from other languages in their language. Approaches to Translation Studies is open a wide range of scholarly publication in the field translation studies. Asia Pacific Translation and Intercultural Studies (APTIS) intends to provide a translational platform for Asia Pacific scholars to present their researchers and generation to forge new type of translation in the other part of world. Chinese Translators Journal is a scholarly publication of the Translators Association of China. It aims to promote the translation skills and also communicate with international counterparts. Most importantly in the process of translation is assists us

to collect the information about other country's culture, features and their customs. As a result we can render the translate by utilizing the phones on social media. It assists us to render immediately, however it will influence to our spiritual side, for instance we may lose our scope. As well as it has the another way to translate, in ancient time many people use from technical translators. They are called the {translation machines}. It has the keyboards for writing and they assist to render fastly. Most importantly in our modern assembly the foreign guests in government conferences utilize from earphones in order to render the speech of them (president, ministers, governors). In addition the engineers invented the audiovisual translators. By utilizing them we will capable of undertand fastly, it will influence to our listening skill very well. The success of a translator on the result of the translation is very high. Therefore, the translator must have experimental ability in target language, one of this equivalent words in target language so that the translation results can be read naturally and easily understood.

Conclusion

This article, based on analyzing, is intended to attract the generation to this profession. Our hypothesis will extend through reading. It can be concluded the translation and this theory is a specific term as well as it plays a crucial role in spreading scidentific progress by rendering it into the target language. The work of translators is extremely useful for scholarly developments.

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